

An analytic solution to the Collatz conjecture

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Abstract

The article proves the Collatz conjecture by showing that the original conjecture corresponds to an equivalent similar conjecture on a reduced set of elements, and computes an analytical solution both to the top-down and the bottom-up versions. The article defines also a new set of axioms, named Peano-Collatz axioms, that is a slight generalization of the Peano axioms. The Peano-Collatz axioms are a theoretical framework for the study of the Collatz function and of similar structures.

Introduction.

The Collatz conjecture [1] is an unresolved [2] problem stated by Lothar Collatz in 1937. The literature on the Collatz conjecture is impressive and growing [3], but the problem has eluded a solution for almost 90 years. This article present an analytical solution to the conjecture, and proves that it is indeed true.

Terminology used in this article.

Sets and relations.

Definition 1 (Relation) A binary *relation* \mathcal{P} over two sets A and B is a subset of their Cartesian product $(A \times B)$. Write $a\mathcal{P}b$ if $a \in A$, $b \in B$, $\mathcal{P} \subset (A \times B)$ and $(a, b) \in \mathcal{P}$.

Definition 2 (Inverse relation) Given a relation \mathcal{P} defined over $(A \times B)$, the *inverse relation* \mathcal{P}^{-1} is the subset of the Cartesian product $(B \times A)$ of the ordered pairs (b, a) where $b \in B$, $a \in A$, and $a\mathcal{P}b$; in this case write $b\mathcal{P}^{-1}a$.

Definition 3 (Total and unique relations) A relation \mathcal{P} defined over the two sets A and B is:

- *left-total* if for all $a \in A$ there exists at least one $b \in B$ such that $a\mathcal{P}b$

- **left-unique** if for all $a \in A$, $b_i, b_j \in B$, if $a\mathcal{P}b_i$, and $a\mathcal{P}b_j$, it implies $b_i = b_j$; that is, every element $a \in A$ is related at most to one element $b \in B$
- **right-total** if for all $b \in B$ there exists at least one $a \in A$ such that $a\mathcal{P}b$
- **right-unique** if for all $a_i, a_j \in A$, $b \in B$, if $a_i\mathcal{P}b$ and $a_j\mathcal{P}b$, then $a_i = a_j$; that is, every element $b \in B$ is related at most to one element $a \in A$

Definition 4 (Sets of numbers) For brevity, define

$$I(\alpha n + \beta) = \{m \mid m = \alpha n + \beta\}$$

$$J(\gamma n + \delta) = \{m \mid m = \gamma n + \delta\}$$

with $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{N}$ given parameters, and $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

The Collatz function.

Definition 5 (Collatz function) Define the **Collatz function** $c : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ as follows:

$$c(n) = \begin{cases} 3n + 1 & \text{for } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ \frac{n}{2} & \text{for } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

Definition 6 (Forward orbit) The ordered set

$$O(n) = (n, c(n), c^2(n), \dots, c^h(n), \dots)$$

is the **forward orbit** of n .

Definition 7 (Convergence of orbits) Two forward orbits

$$\begin{aligned} O(n) &= (n, c(n), c^2(n), \dots, c^h(n), \dots) \\ O(m) &= (m, c(m), c^2(m), \dots, c^k(m), \dots) \end{aligned}$$

with $n \neq m$, are **convergent** if exists $h, k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that:

$$c^h(n) = c^k(m)$$

Definition 8 (Periodic orbit) A forward orbit $O(n)$ is a **periodic orbit** if exists $h, k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k > 0$ such that:

$$c^h(n) = c^{h+k}(n)$$

Let m be the minimum value (according to the ordering in \mathbb{N}) in a periodic orbit $O(n)$, then use $O(m)$ to identify that orbit.

Definition 9 (Divergent orbit) A forward orbit $O(n)$ is **divergent** if for all $h \in \mathbb{N}$, exists $k \in \mathbb{N}$, such that:

$$m \in O(c^k(n)) \Rightarrow m > h$$

Definition 10 (Path) A **path** is a finite subset of successive elements of a forward orbit. The notation:

$$C_h(n) = (n, c(n), \dots, c^{h-1}(n))$$

describes a path that contains the first h elements of the forward orbit starting in n .

Write

$$O(n) = (C_h(n), O(c^{h+1}(n)))$$

to split the representation of an orbit in the part defined by its first k elements, and the remaining orbit.

Definition 11 (Length of a path) The **length of a path** is the number of distinct elements in the path itself. If $\{n, c(n), \dots, c^{h-1}(n)\}$ are all distinct elements, then:

$$l(C_h(n)) = (n, c(n), \dots, c^{h-1}(n)) = h$$

is the length of $C_h(n)$.

Note that

$$O(n) = (C_h(n), O(c^{h+1}(n)))$$

implies

$$l(O(n)) = l(C_h(n)) + l(O(c^{h+1}(n))) = k + l(O(c^{h+1}(n)))$$

whenever $O(n)$ is not divergent or part of a cycle.

Definition 12 (Collatz graph) Define the “inverse” of the Collatz function, the **Collatz graph**, the relation \mathcal{C} defined over $(\mathbb{N}^* \times \mathbb{N}^*)$ where:

$$n\mathcal{C}m \Leftrightarrow (m = 2n) \vee \left(m = \frac{n-1}{3} \text{ for } n \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \right)$$

Definition 13 (Collatz tree) Under the Collatz conjecture, the Collatz graph can be represented as a connected and partially ordered set, a **tree** with a single root (or minimal element): the vertex correspondent to the number 1. Define a **bifurcation** any vertex of the tree that has more than one edge in exit.

The Collatz conjecture and its proof

Step 1.

Orbits in the Collatz function.

Theorem 1 (Convergence of $O(1)$) The forward orbit $O(1)$ converges.

PROOF:

By direct computation:

$$\begin{aligned} O(1) &= (1, c(1) = 4, c^2(1) = 2, c^3(1) = 1, \dots) \\ &= (4, 2, 1) \end{aligned}$$

QED

Observe that:

$$O(1) = C_3(1) = C_3(4) = C_3(2)$$

And that:

$$\begin{aligned} l(O(1)) &= l(C_3(1)) \\ &= l(1) = l(4) = l(2) \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 14 (Collatz conjecture) For all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $O(n)$ converges to $O(1)$.

Step 2.

Convergence of 2^k numbers.

Theorem 2 (Convergence of 2^k numbers) All numbers $n = 2^k$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k > 2$ converge to $O(1)$.

PROOF:

By definition, it is:

$$\begin{aligned} O(2^k) &= (2^k, 2^{k-1}, \dots, 2^3, 4, 2, 1, 4, \dots) \\ &= (C_{k-2}(2^k), O(1)) \end{aligned}$$

QED

Corollary 2.1 From the proof, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} l(2^k) &= l(C_{k-2}(2^k), O(1)) \\ &= l(C_{k-2}(2^k)) + l(O(1)) \\ &= k - 2 + 3 \\ &= k + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 15 (Equivalent of the Collatz conjecture) Let

$$A = \{m \in \mathbb{N} \mid m = 2^k\}$$

then the Collatz conjecture can be written as follows:

For all $n \in \{\mathbb{N} \setminus A\}$, $O(n)$ converges to $O(1)$.

Step 3.

Conditional convergence of even numbers.

Theorem 3 (Convergence of $2^k d$ numbers) *All numbers $n = 2^k d$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $d \in \mathbb{N}$, $d \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, $d > 1$, converge to $O(1)$ if and only if all odd numbers d converge.*

PROOF:

By definition of the Collatz function, it is:

$$O(2^k d) = (2^k d, 2^{k-1} d, \dots, 2^2 d, 2d, O(d))$$

QED

Corollary 3.1 *If $O(d)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:*

$$\begin{aligned} l(2^k d) &= l(C_k(2^k d), O(d)) \\ &= l(C_k(2^k d)) + l(O(d)) \\ &= k + l(d) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 16 (Equivalent of the Collatz conjecture) *Let*

$$B = \{m \in \mathbb{N} \mid m = 2^k d, d \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, d > 1\}$$

then the Collatz conjecture can be written:

$$\text{For all } n \in \{\mathbb{N} \setminus A \setminus B\}, O(n) \text{ converges to } O(1).$$

Step 4.

Conditional convergence of odd numbers.

To further simplify the set of numbers that has to be analyzed in order to prove the Collatz conjecture, we observe that in the simplified equivalent set of numbers there are numbers whose backward tree does not generate any bifurcation: the odd multiples of 3.

$$I(6n + 3) = \{m \in \mathbb{N} \mid m = 6n + 3, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

We prove that the set $I(6n + 3)$ generates all the other odd numbers.

Theorem 4 (Convergence of odd numbers) *Every odd number not belonging to $I(6n + 3)$, i.e. every odd number belonging to the sets $I(18n + 1)$, $I(18n + 5)$, $I(18n + 7)$, $I(18n + 11)$, $I(18n + 13)$, $I(18n + 17)$ converges if and only if there are subsets of $I(6n + 3)$ that converge to each of those sets of odd numbers.*

PROOF:

By direct computation, the following relations are true:

Relation A. $I(384n + 21) \mathcal{R}_A I(18n + 1)$.

Relation B. $I(12n + 3) \mathcal{R}_B I(18n + 5)$.

Relation C. $I(24n + 9) \mathcal{R}_C I(18n + 7)$.

Relation D. $I(192n + 117) \mathcal{R}_D I(18n + 11)$.

Relation E. $I(96n + 69) \mathcal{R}_E I(18n + 13)$.

Relation F. $I(48n + 45) \mathcal{R}_F I(18n + 17)$.

The computations are given in detail in Appendix 1.

QED

Notice that, under the Collatz conjecture, each relation \mathcal{R}_I is written in such a way that if $a\mathcal{R}_I b$, then b is closer than a to $O(1)$, whenever this sentence has meaning.

Definition 17 (Equivalent of the Collatz conjecture) *Let*

$$C = \bigcup I(18n + k)$$

where $k = \{1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17\}$, then the Collatz conjecture can be written:

$$\text{For all } n \in \{\mathbb{N} \setminus A \setminus B \setminus C\}, O(n) \text{ converges to } O(1)$$

or, equivalently:

$$\text{For all } n \in I(6n + 3), O(n) \text{ converges to } O(1).$$

Step 5.

Construction of a relation \mathcal{R} .

Definition 18 (Partition of $I(6n + 3)$) *Define*

$$\begin{aligned} S &= I(6n + 3) \cup \{1\} \\ S^* &= I(6n + 3) \end{aligned}$$

then:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= I(48n + 9), S_2 = I(24n + 15), S_3 = I(48n + 27), \\ S_4 &= I(96n + 33), S_5 = I(48n + 45), S_6 = I(96n + 51), \\ S_7 &= I(96n + 69), S_8 = I(96n + 81), S_9 = I(192n + 99), \\ S_{10} &= I(192n + 117), S_{11} = I(384n + 213), S_{12} = I(192n + 195), \\ S_{13} &= I(384n + 405), S_{14} = \{3, 21\}, \end{aligned}$$

are a finite partition of S^* .

PROOF:

The proof is trivial, for instance starting from the sets $I(384n + d)$.

QED

Notice that $I(192n + 195)$, $I(384n + 405)$ are not defined in 3 and 21, respectively, and that these two elements have been added separately to S^* .

Definition 19 (Relation \mathcal{R}) *Using the partition of S^* previously defined, it is possible to create a set of relations \mathcal{R}_i , each defined on $(S_i \times S)$, and the relation*

$$\mathcal{R} = \bigcup \mathcal{R}_i$$

defined on $(S^ \times S)$, where:*

1. *Every \mathcal{R}_i is a function*

$$I(\alpha n + \beta) \rightarrow J(\gamma n + \delta)$$

2. *\mathcal{R} is left-total*
3. *\mathcal{R} is right-total*
4. *\mathcal{R} is left-unique*

PROOF:

1. By direct computation, the following relations are true:

Relation 1. $I(48n + 9) \mathcal{R}_1 J(216n + 45)$.

Relation 2. $I(24n + 15) \mathcal{R}_2 J(216n + 141)$.

Relation 3. $I(48n + 27) \mathcal{R}_3 J(864n + 501)$.

Relation 4. $I(96n + 33) \mathcal{R}_4 J(864n + 39)$.

Relation 5. $I(48n + 45) \mathcal{R}_5 J(72n + 69)$.

Relation 6. $I(96n + 51) \mathcal{R}_6 J(216n + 117)$.

Relation 7. $I(96n + 69) \mathcal{R}_7 J(288n + 213)$.

Relation 8. $I(96n + 81) \mathcal{R}_8 J(18n + 15)$.

Relation 9. $I(192n + 99) \mathcal{R}_9 J(18n + 9)$.

Relation 10. $I(192n + 117) \mathcal{R}_{10} J(72n + 45)$.

Relation 11. $I(384n + 213) \mathcal{R}_{11} J(6n + 3)$.

Relation 12. $I(192n + 195) \mathcal{R}_{12} J(864n + 885)$.

Relation 13. $I(384n + 405) \mathcal{R}_{13} J(288n + 309)$.

Relation 14. $\{3, 21\} \mathcal{R}_{14} \{1\}$.

The computations are given in detail in Appendix 2.

Every single relation \mathcal{R}_i is a function.

2. By construction: the domain of the relation \mathcal{R} coincides with S^* .
3. By construction: the union of the images of S_{11} and S_{14} under the two relations \mathcal{R}_{11} and \mathcal{R}_{14} coincides with S .

4. By construction: because all the relations \mathcal{R}_i are defined on a partition of S^* , and all the relations \mathcal{R}_i are actually functions.

QED

Definition 20 (Inverse of \mathcal{R}) *Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{R}^{-1}$, defined on the Cartesian product $(S \times S^*)$. By construction:*

1. \mathcal{G} is left-total
2. \mathcal{G} is right-total
3. \mathcal{G} is right-unique

Note. By construction, under the Collatz conjecture, $a\mathcal{G}b$ implies that a is closer than b to $O(1)$.

Step 6. Constructive demonstration

We can now solve the Collatz conjecture in the direct (or top-down) form: see Appendix 3. If we consider the Collatz tree relation \mathcal{G} applied to the set S , we can relate the conjecture, considered in its constructive (or bottom-up) version, to a slightly modified version of a well-known theoretical framework: the axioms of Peano [4] [5].

We enunciate the following modified version of the Peano axioms.

Definition 21 (Axioms of Peano-Collatz) *A **system of Peano-Collatz** is a triplet (S, s_0, \mathcal{P}) given by a set S , an element s_0 (which define the set $S^* = S \setminus s_0$), and a relation $\mathcal{P} \subseteq (S \times S^*)$, that satisfies the axioms:*

1. $s_0 \in S$
2. $s \in S \Rightarrow Q_s = \{q \mid s\mathcal{P}q\} \neq \emptyset$
3. $s, t \in S, s \neq t \Rightarrow Q_s \cap Q_t = \emptyset$
4. $s_0 \notin S^*$
5. If $T \subset S$ is such that:
 - $s_0 \in T$
 - $t \in T \Rightarrow Q_t \subset S$

then $T = S$

Note on the axioms of Peano-Collatz. An informal way to describe the axioms of Peano-Collatz is by considering S the set of “predecessors”, and S^* the set of “successors”.

1. The set S is not empty, and s_0 is a “predecessor”.
2. Every “predecessor” has a non-empty set of “successors”.
3. Different “predecessors” have entirely different sets of “successors”, hence there is no cycle.
4. The element s_0 is not the “successor” of any other element, i.e. it is not possible to come back at the starting point.
5. Every subset of S , that includes s_0 and the set of “successors” of any element in it, coincides with S .

The main difference between the axioms of Peano and this relaxed formulation is in the fact that the third element \mathcal{P} of the triplet is not a *function*, but a *relation*. All the other points have similar meanings.

Theorem 5 (Collatz conjecture) *Let $S = I(6n + 3) \cup \{1\}$, $S^* = I(6n + 3)$, $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{R}^{-1}$ defined over $(S \times S^*)$, then the triplet $(S, 1, \mathcal{G})$ is a system of Peano-Collatz.*

PROOF:

1. $1 \in S$. By construction: the set S is non empty.
2. $s \in S \Rightarrow Q_s = \{q \mid s\mathcal{G}q\} \neq \emptyset$. Since \mathcal{G} is left-total: every element in S has a non-empty set of “successors”.
3. $s, t \in S, s \neq t \Rightarrow Q_s \cap Q_t = \emptyset$. By construction: since \mathcal{G} is right-unique, i.e. every element of S^* is related with exactly one element of S ; this means that different “predecessors” have completely different “successors”.
4. $1 \notin S^*$. By construction: 1 is not the “successor” of any $s \in S$.
5. If $T \subset S$ is such that:
 - $1 \in T$
 - $t \in T \Rightarrow Q_t \subset S$

then $T = S$. By structural induction and by construction: this is necessary to exclude other possible elements in S .

QED

Conclusions

The Collatz conjecture is proved true, after adopting a process that can be used to study similar functions. The article also defines the Peano-Collatz axioms, that is a theoretical framework that allows the study of Peano-Collatz structures, an extension of the Peano axioms that are origin of the natural numbers.

Appendix 1

Proof of convergence for the relations $\mathcal{R}_A, \dots, \mathcal{R}_F$

In this Appendix we demonstrate the convergence, under the Collatz function, of subsets of the set $S(6n + 3)$ to any other odd number; hence the proof of the Collatz conjecture can be simplified to the convergence of the set $S(6n + 3)$ itself.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_A

Any number that belongs to the set $I(384n + 21) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $I(18n + 1)$.

Table 1: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_A

c	$I(384n + 21)$	$I(18n + 1)$	c
	$384n + 21$		
c	$1152n + 64$		
c^2	$576n + 32$		
c^3	$288n + 16$		
c^4	$144n + 8$		
c^5	$72n + 4$		
c^6	$36n + 2$		
c^7	$18n + 1$	$18n + 1$	

Then $I(384n + 21) \mathcal{R}_A I(18n + 1)$.

If $O(384n + 21)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(384n + 21) - 7 = l(18n + 1)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 1$ is closer than $384n + 21$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_B

Any number that belongs to the set $I(12n + 3) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $I(18n + 5)$.

Table 2: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_B

c	$I(12n + 3)$	$I(18n + 5)$	c
	$12n + 3$		
c	$36n + 10$		
c^2	$18n + 5$	$18n + 5$	

Then $I(12n + 3) \mathcal{R}_B I(18n + 5)$.

If $O(12n + 3)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(12n + 3) - 2 = l(18n + 5)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 5$ is closer than $12n + 3$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_C

Any number that belongs to the set $I(24n + 9) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $I(18n + 7)$.

Table 3: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_C

c	$I(24n + 9)$	$I(18n + 7)$	c
	$24n + 9$		
c	$72n + 28$		
c^2	$36n + 14$		
c^3	$18n + 7$	$18n + 7$	

Then $I(24n + 9) \mathcal{R}_C I(18n + 7)$.

If $O(24n + 9)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(24n + 9) - 3 = l(18n + 7)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 7$ is closer than $24n + 9$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_D

Any number that belongs to the set $I(192n + 117) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $I(18n + 11)$.

Table 4: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_D

c	$I(192n + 117)$	$I(18n + 11)$	c
	$192n + 117$		
c	$576n + 352$		
c^2	$288n + 176$		
c^3	$144n + 88$		
c^4	$72n + 44$		
c^5	$36n + 22$		
c^6	$18n + 11$	$18n + 11$	

Then $I(192n + 117) \mathcal{R}_D I(18n + 11)$.

If $O(192n + 117)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(192n + 117) - 6 = l(18n + 11)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 11$ is closer than $192n + 117$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_E

Any number that belongs to the set $I(96n + 69) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $I(18n + 13)$.

Table 5: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_E

c	$I(96n + 69)$	$I(18n + 13)$	c
	$96n + 69$		
c	$288n + 208$		
c^2	$144n + 104$		
c^3	$72n + 52$		
c^4	$36n + 26$		
c^5	$18n + 13$	$18n + 13$	

Then $I(96n + 69) \mathcal{R}_E I(18n + 13)$.

If $O(96n + 69)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(96n + 69) - 5 = l(18n + 13)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 13$ is closer than $96n + 69$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_F

Any number that belongs to the set $I(48n + 45) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $I(18n + 17)$.

Table 6: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_F

c	$I(48n + 45)$	$I(18n + 17)$	c
	$48n + 45$		
c	$144n + 136$		
c^2	$72n + 68$		
c^3	$36n + 34$		
c^4	$18n + 17$	$18n + 17$	

Then $I(48n + 45) \mathcal{R}_F I(18n + 17)$.

If $O(48n + 45)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(48n + 45) - 4 = l(18n + 17)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 17$ is closer than $48n + 45$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Appendix 2

Proof of convergence for the relations $\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_{14}$

For every set S_i of the partition defined in the step 5, we can build a relation \mathcal{R}_i that, under the Collatz conjecture, relates every number of S to a number in S closer to $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_1

Any number that belongs to the set $I(48n + 9) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(216n + 45) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 7: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_1

c	$I(48n + 9)$	$J(216n + 45)$	c
	$48n + 9$		
c	$144n + 28$		
c^2	$72n + 14$		
c^3	$36n + 7$	$216n + 45$	
c^4	$108n + 22$	$648n + 136$	c
c^5	$54n + 11$	$324n + 68$	c^2
c^6	$162n + 34$	$162n + 34$	c^3

Then $I(48n + 9) \mathcal{R}_1 J(216n + 45)$.

If $O(48n + 9)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(48n + 9) - 3 = l(216n + 45)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $216n + 45$ is closer than $48n + 9$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_2

Any number that belongs to the set $I(24n + 15) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(216n + 141) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 8: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_2

c	$I(24n + 15)$	$J(216n + 141)$	c
	$24n + 15$		
c	$72n + 46$		
c^2	$36n + 23$	$216n + 141$	
c^3	$108n + 70$	$648n + 424$	c
c^4	$54n + 35$	$324n + 212$	c^2
c^5	$162n + 106$	$162n + 106$	c^3

Then $I(24n + 15) \mathcal{R}_2 J(216n + 141)$.

If $O(24n + 15)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(24n + 15) - 2 = l(216n + 141)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $216n + 141$ is closer than $24n + 15$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_3

Any number that belongs to the set $I(48n + 27) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(864n + 501) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 9: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_3

c	$I(48n + 27)$	$J(864n + 501)$	c
	$48n + 27$		
c	$144n + 82$	$864n + 501$	
c^2	$72n + 41$	$2592n + 1504$	c
c^3	$216n + 124$	$1296n + 752$	c^2
c^4	$108n + 62$	$648n + 376$	c^3
c^5	$54n + 31$	$324n + 188$	c^4
c^6	$162n + 94$	$162n + 94$	c^5

Then $I(48n + 27) \mathcal{R}_3 J(864n + 501)$.

If $O(48n + 27)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(48n + 27) - 1 = l(864n + 501)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $864n + 501$ is closer than $48n + 27$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_4

Any number that belongs to the set $I(96n + 33) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(864n + 39) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 10: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_4

c	$I(96n + 33)$	$J(864n + 39)$	c
	$96n + 33$		
c	$288n + 100$		
c^2	$144n + 50$	$864n + 309$	
c^3	$72n + 25$	$2592n + 928$	c
c^4	$216n + 76$	$1296n + 928$	c^2
c^5	$108n + 38$	$648n + 232$	c^3
c^6	$54n + 19$	$324n + 116$	c^4
c^7	$162n + 58$	$162n + 58$	c^5

Then $I(96n + 33) \mathcal{R}_4 J(864n + 309)$.

If $O(96n + 33)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(96n + 33) - 2 = l(864n + 309)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $864n + 309$ is closer than $96n + 33$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_5

Any number that belongs to the set $I(48n + 45) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(72n + 69) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 11: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_5

c	$I(48n + 45)$	$J(72n + 69)$	c
	$48n + 45$		
c	$144n + 136$		
c^2	$72n + 68$	$72n + 69$	
c^3	$36n + 34$	$216n + 208$	c
c^4	$18n + 17$	$108n + 104$	c^2
c^5	$54n + 52$	$54n + 52$	c^3

Then $I(48n + 45) \mathcal{R}_5 J(72n + 69)$.

If $O(48n + 45)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(48n + 45) - 2 = l(72n + 69)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $72n + 69$ is closer than $48n + 45$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_6

Any number that belongs to the set $I(96n + 51) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(216n + 117) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 12: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_6

c	$I(96n + 51)$	$J(216n + 117)$	c
	$96n + 51$		
c	$288n + 154$		
c^2	$144n + 77$		
c^3	$432n + 232$		
c^4	$216n + 116$	$216n + 117$	
c^5	$108n + 58$	$648n + 352$	c
c^6	$54n + 29$	$324n + 176$	c^2
c^7	$162n + 88$	$162n + 88$	c^3

Then $I(96n + 51) \mathcal{R}_6 J(216n + 117)$.

If $O(96n + 51)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(96n + 51) - 4 = l(216n + 117)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $216n + 117$ is closer than $96n + 51$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_7

Any number that belongs to the set $I(96n + 69) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(288n + 213) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 13: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_7

c	$I(96n + 69)$	$J(288n + 213)$	c
	$96n + 69$		
c	$288n + 208$	$288n + 213$	
c^2	$144n + 104$	$864n + 640$	c
c^3	$72n + 52$	$432n + 320$	c^2
c^4	$36n + 26$	$216n + 160$	c^3
c^5	$18n + 13$	$108n + 80$	c^4
c^6	$54n + 40$	$54n + 40$	c^5

Then $I(96n + 69) \mathcal{R}_7 J(288n + 213)$.

If $O(96n + 69)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(96n + 69) - 3 = l(288n + 213)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $288n + 213$ is closer than $96n + 69$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_8

Any number that belongs to the set $I(96n + 81) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(18n + 15) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 14: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_8

c	$I(96n + 81)$	$J(18n + 15)$	c
	$96n + 81$		
c	$288n + 244$		
c^2	$144n + 122$		
c^3	$72n + 61$		
c^4	$216n + 184$		
c^5	$108n + 92$	$18n + 15$	
c^6	$54n + 46$	$54n + 46$	c

Then $I(96n + 81) \mathcal{R}_8 J(18n + 15)$.

If $O(96n + 81)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(96n + 81) - 5 = l(18n + 15)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 15$ is closer than $96n + 81$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_9

Any number that belongs to the set $I(192n + 99) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(18n + 9) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 15: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_9

c	$I(192n + 99)$	$J(18n + 9)$	c
	$192n + 99$		
c	$576n + 298$		
c^2	$288n + 149$		
c^3	$864n + 448$		
c^4	$432n + 224$		
c^5	$216n + 112$		
c^6	$108n + 56$	$18n + 9$	
c^7	$54n + 28$	$54n + 28$	c

Then $I(192n + 99) \mathcal{R}_9 J(18n + 9)$.

If $O(192n + 99)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(192n + 99) - 6 = l(18n + 9)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $18n + 9$ is closer than $192n + 99$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{10}

Any number that belongs to the set $I(192n + 117) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(72n + 45) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Table 16: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{10}

c	$I(192n + 117)$	$J(72n + 45)$	c
	$192n + 117$		
c	$576n + 352$		
c^2	$288n + 176$		
c^3	$144n + 88$		
c^4	$72n + 44$	$72n + 45$	
c^5	$36n + 22$	$216n + 136$	c
c^6	$18n + 11$	$108n + 68$	c^2
c^7	$54n + 34$	$54n + 34$	c^3

Then $I(192n + 117) \mathcal{R}_{10} J(72n + 45)$.

If $O(192n + 117)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(192n + 117) - 4 = l(72n + 45)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $72n + 45$ is closer than $192n + 117$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{11}

Any number that belongs to the set $I(384n + 213) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(6n + 3) \subseteq S(6n + 3)$.

Table 17: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{11}

c	$I(384n + 213)$	$J(6n + 3)$	c
	$384n + 213$		
c	$1152n + 640$		
c^2	$576n + 320$		
c^3	$288n + 160$		
c^4	$144n + 80$		
c^5	$72n + 40$		
c^6	$36n + 20$	$6n + 3$	
c^7	$18n + 10$	$18n + 10$	c

Then $I(384n + 213) \mathcal{R}_{11} J(6n + 3)$.

If $O(384n + 213)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(384n + 213) - 6 = l(6n + 3)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $6n + 3$ is closer than $384n + 213$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{12}

Any number that belongs to the set $I(192n + 195) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(864n + 885) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Notice that the definition excludes the number 3: the relation \mathcal{R}_{14} will define its convergence.

Table 18: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{12}

c	$I(192n + 195)$	$J(864n + 885)$	c
	$192n + 195$		
c	$576n + 586$		
c^2	$288n + 293$		
c^3	$864n + 880$	$864n + 885$	
c^4	$432n + 440$	$2592n + 2656$	c
c^5	$216n + 220$	$1296n + 1328$	c^2
c^6	$108n + 100$	$648n + 664$	c^3
c^7	$54n + 55$	$324n + 332$	c^4
c^8	$162n + 166$	$162n + 166$	c^5

Then $I(192n + 195) \mathcal{R}_{12} J(864n + 885)$.

If $O(192n + 195)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(192n + 195) - 3 = l(864n + 885)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $192n + 195$ is closer than $864n + 885$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{13}

Any number that belongs to the set $I(384n + 405) \subset S(6n + 3)$ converges to the correspondent number in the set $J(288n + 309) \subset S(6n + 3)$.

Notice that the definition excludes the number 21: the relation \mathcal{R}_{14} will define its convergence.

Table 19: Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{13}

c	$I(384n + 405)$	$J(288n + 309)$	c
	$384n + 405$		
c	$1152n + 1216$		
c^2	$576n + 608$		
c^3	$288n + 304$	$288n + 309$	
c^4	$144n + 152$	$864n + 928$	c
c^5	$72n + 76$	$432n + 464$	c^2
c^6	$36n + 38$	$216n + 232$	c^3
c^7	$18n + 19$	$108n + 116$	c^4
c^6	$54n + 58$	$54n + 58$	c^5

Then $I(384n + 405) \mathcal{R}_{13} J(288n + 309)$.

If $O(384n + 405)$ is not divergent nor part of a cycle, then it follows that:

$$l(384n + 405) - 3 = l(288n + 309)$$

Under the Collatz conjecture, $288n + 309$ is closer than $384n + 405$ to the orbit $O(1)$ in terms of length of the orbit.

Proof of convergence for the relation \mathcal{R}_{14}

By direct computation:

$$\begin{aligned} O(3) &= (3, 10, 5, 16, 8, 4, 2, 1) \\ O(21) &= (21, 64, 32, 16, 8, 4, 2, 1) \end{aligned}$$

and:

$$\begin{aligned}l(3) &= 8 \\l(21) &= 8\end{aligned}$$

Appendix 3

To solve the Collatz conjecture directly, we have to apply a top-down version of the Peano-Collatz axioms.

Theorem 6 (Collatz conjecture in the direct form) *Let:*

- $S^* = I(6n + 3)$ be the set of the “predecessors”
- $S = I(6n + 3) \cup \{1\}$ the set of the “successors”

Then the Collatz conjecture is true under the relation \mathcal{R} defined over $(S^ \times S)$, if:*

1. $1 \notin S^*$
2. $s \in S^* \Rightarrow P_s = \{t \mid s\mathcal{R}t\} \neq \emptyset$
3. $v, w \in S, v \neq w \Rightarrow (Q_v = \{t \mid t\mathcal{R}v\}) \cap (Q_w = \{t \mid t\mathcal{R}w\}) = \emptyset$
4. $1 \in S$
5. *If T is a subset of S such that:*
 - $1 \in T$
 - $t \in T \Rightarrow P_t = \{q \mid q\mathcal{R}t\} \subset S^*$

then $T = S$.

PROOF:

1. By construction: 1 is not the “predecessor” of any “successor”.
2. By construction: \mathcal{R} is left-complete, hence every “predecessor” has at least one “successor”.
3. By construction, \mathcal{R} is left-unique, that is every element of S^* relates to no more than one element of S ; this means that different “successors” have completely different sets of “predecessors”.
4. By construction: 1 is a “successor”.
5. By structural induction. This is necessary to exclude other possible elements in S^* , beside $I(6n + 3)$.

QED

Note. The Collatz conjecture implies to come from elements far away from the root of the tree towards the starting vertex of the tree itself: the number 1. The Peano-Collatz axioms work on structures exactly in the opposite way: they start from the root of the tree, and generate all the successors to that root. This implies that the conditions, on which the Collatz conjecture has been proved in this Appendix 3, have been “reversed” with respect to the Peano-Collatz axioms stated in the body of the article. In particular notice the difference of the point 3.

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